

How Internodal Spacing Modulates Saltatory Information Flow

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Abstract

In this note, the authors simulate action potential propagation in an axon tract under different conditions of internodal spacing and find that this plays a critical role in information propagation.

We modify the model in [1] so that the internodal spacing is not fixed. In any biological system the internodal spacing will show slight variations from nodal pair to nodal pair. In this note we exaggerate these differences and study a few different types of internodal spacing profiles. These include: linear growth, exponential growth, exponential decay and so on.

The figures below are self explanatory. Each shows the voltage on the vertical axis and time on the horizontal axis. Each shows one or more nodal voltage profiles for the corresponding internodal spacing profile.

In Figures 10 through 13 the authors compute the Green's function approximation to the action potential profile that was derived in [2] for the various spacing profiles and various time instants. As Figure 8 in [2] indicates, plotting the Green function at a particular time shows the action potential profile in the absence of nodes.

References

- [1] Aman Chawla, Salvatore Morgera, and Arthur Snider. On axon interaction and its role in neurological networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*, 2019.
- [2] Arthur Snider, Aman Chawla, and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. Axonal conduction velocity: A computer study. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 12:60–71.

Figure 1: Sinusoidal.

Figure 2: Exponential Decay.

Figure 3: Exponential Growth.

Figure 4: Linear growth.

Figure 5: Quadratic Growth.

Figure 6: Logarithmic growth.

Figure 7: Cubic growth.

Figure 8: Harmonic growth.

Figure 9: Custom polynomial growth.

Figure 10: Variation of the Green's function profile with internodal spacing L for a fixed internodal propagation time. The internodal spacing L itself is a function of the distance along the axon due to the various spacing profiles indicated in the legend. The time instant considered is $t=0.0008s$.

Figure 11: Variation of the Green's function profile with internodal spacing L for a fixed internodal propagation time. The internodal spacing L itself is a function of the distance along the axon due to the various spacing profiles indicated in the legend. The time instant considered is $t=0.08\text{s}$.

Figure 12: Variation of the Green's function profile with internodal spacing L for a fixed internodal propagation time. The internodal spacing L itself is a function of the distance along the axon due to the various spacing profiles indicated in the legend. The time instant considered is $t=0.8s$.

Figure 13: Variation of the Green's function profile with internodal spacing L for a fixed internodal propagation time. The internodal spacing L itself is a function of the distance along the axon due to the various spacing profiles indicated in the legend. The time instant considered is $t=1.5s$.